

APPLYING MACHINE LEARNING TO PREDICT MELASMA

Ho Van Lam⁽¹⁾, Vu Tuan Anh⁽²⁾, Pham Thi Hoang Bich Diu⁽²⁾, Tran Xuan Viet⁽²⁾

1. Faculty of Information Technology, Quy Nhon University.

2. Quyhoa National Leprosy Dermatology Hospital, Binh Dinh, Vietnam.

Email: hovanlam@qnu.edu.vn; drvtavn@gmail.com; bichdiuqnqh@gmail.com; thstranxuanviet@gmail.com

Abstract - This study aims to predict Melasma based on users' data combined with medical practice data community by dermatologists to predict the disease and make some necessary recommendations in the patient screening. This study also helps reduce treatment costs and supports remote patient treatment. In this study, we built a machine learning model to assist dermatologists in predicting a person's risk of Melasma after entering his/her community information. People can use this model through an application to track their risk of Melasma. Combining input community data with the expertise of Melasma specialists, we built a dataset with relevant information to predict Melasma. Based on this dataset, we have statistically described the data characteristics as well as the correlated data parameters that may cause Melasma, then we use the XGBoost algorithm to build a machine learning model to predict whether a person is infected to Melasma or not. The obtained results are going to be applied to assist in predicting whether a person may have Melasma with the input of community information combined with medical practice knowledge about the disease. From this result, it is possible to continue researching and applying artificial intelligence to support diagnosis and treatment of Melasma.

Key words: XGBoost algorithm, Melasma disease, machine learning, Melasma prediction.

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine Learning is a field of Artificial Intelligence, which is a technique that helps computers learn on their own without setting up decision rules. Normally, a computer program needs rules to be able to execute a certain task, but with machine learning, computers can automatically execute the task upon receiving input data. In other words, machine learning means that computers can think on their own like humans. Another approach argues that machine learning is a method of drawing lines that represents the relationship of a data set [1], [5], [13]. Combining the expertise of dermatologists with people's public information on Melasma [10], we used data analysis techniques to show correlations features of the data: descriptive analysis, visualisation data may help experts and people easily monitor the possibility of having Melasma through input data of a person's daily information. From the results of the analysis, we built a machine learning

model with the input data of expertise of dermatologists specializing in Melasma combined with patients' community information, so that computer can support to predict whether a person is infected to Melasma or not. The machine learning model was built based on XGBoost algorithm, a machine learning algorithm that is evaluated to have numerous advantages [8]. In this study, the machine learning model using the XGBoost algorithm to predict whether a person is at risk of getting Melasma and how much the probability is. The adjustment of parameters to optimize the model is also done in this paper through analyzing some properties of the model such as Cross validation, Learning Curves, confusion matrix, ROC-AUC curve, Precision-Recall curve and data variables that affect the predictive model. Approach some Model Evaluation methods to evaluate the results obtained from the model, evaluate whether the model has met the set goals or not, analyze the indicators achieved by the model, and make decisions on the use of the analysis results in practice. We also showed how the deployment has been done at Quyhoa National Leprosy Dermatology Hospital where our machine learning model is used in a web application to help users predict the likelihood of Melasma after providing some survey information.

II. DATA IN MELASMA DISEASE

Melasma is an acquired hypermelanosis with complex etiology and pathogenesis. The primary lesion of the disease is macules and/or dark brown, symmetrical patches in sun-exposed areas. Common sites of infection are the cheeks, upper lip, chin, and forehead. Though the disease is benign, it greatly affects the psychology and aesthetics of the patients [9]. In women, the disease can be idiopathic or related to pregnancy [10].

Descriptive statistics (age, geographical distribution, group of facial hyperpigmentation disease, education level, occupation, marital status, maternity history, family history in Melasma, medical history and cosmetics use...) were measured by frequency and percentage. From the collected data, we remove inadequate data and build a Melasma prediction model.

The data set used in training and testing the machine learning model was collected from the community through a survey. The data set includes 21 data fields containing information of persons to be checked and medical practice information with a total of 795 recorded samples organized as .csv files.

Descriptive analysis from the data set helps us to get some more information such as variables of clinical characteristics data and daily habit factors for Melasma. Through this data descriptive analysis, we also obtained clinical characteristics-independent variables such as age, occupation, ethnicity, comorbidities, family history... as well as habit-independent variables such as sun exposure, cosmetic use, pregnancy, and oral contraceptive use. This makes the training, evaluation and model correction process more effective.

From the age information in the data set, we have the age distribution of people who are likely to have Melasma in Figure 1. It is shown in the Figure that 35-45-year-old subjects have a high probability of Melasma.

Figure 1. Distribution of Melasma by age

In terms of family economic status, the analysis results also indicate that the proportion of poor and near-poor patients with Melasma is higher than that of the non-poor group. A multivariable logistic regression analysis reveals that the poor and near-poor groups have a 3.91 times higher risk of Melasma than the non-poor group.

The analysis also shows that the percentage of Melasma patients who are pregnant is higher than that of Melasma patients who are not. A multivariate logistic regression analysis indicates that those with a history of Melasma during pregnancy have a 2.93 times higher risk of Melasma compared with those without a history of Melasma during pregnancy as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of Melasma by history of Melasma during pregnancy

Occupation is also indicated to have an influence on possibility of Melasma as in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of Melasma by occupation

Cosmetics use is another influential factor of Melasma. A multivariable logistic regression analysis shows that the use of whitening cosmetics increases the risk of Melasma by 1.5 times compared to the group that do not use, which is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Distribution of Melasma by Cosmetics use

The dataset includes 21 features: Birthcontrolpills, Occupation, FamilyEconomy, Melasmaduringpregnancy, Religion, Familyhistory, Monthofpregnancy, Morning, Afternoon, Numberofpregnancies, Usingcosmetics, Noon, Numberofhoursofsunlightexposure, Yearofbird, Ageofusingcosmetics, Pathology, Marriage, Education, Numberofbirths, Ethnicity, Chemical exposure and analyzed their correlation so that we have more insight about the dataset in Figure 5. Correlation analysis used to study the strength of a relationship and possible connections between features in dataset.

Through correlation analysis we get ranking of correlation coefficients; Example: Pair (Numberofpregnancies, Numberofbirths) is 98% or pair (Morning, Afternoon) is 42% and so on, from there it helps us to make accurate assessments and provide solutions to upgrade our machine learning model.

Figure 5. Correlation analysis in the data set

From the dataset and the results of the dataset analysis above, to predict whether a person is infected to Melasma or not we chose XGBoost algorithm for machine learning model with the input data of expertise of dermatologists specializing in Melasma combined with patients' community information. XGBoost is short for eXtreme Gradient Boosting. It is an efficient and scalable implementation of gradient boosting framework [1], [8], [14]. It has several features: 1. Speed: XGBoost can automatically do parallel computation. 2. Input Type: XGBoost takes several types of input data: Dense Matrix, Sparse Matrix, Data File. 3. Sparsity: XGBoost accepts sparse input for both tree booster and linear booster, and is optimized for sparse input. 4. Customization: XGBoost supports customized objective function and evaluation function. 5. Performance: XGBoost has better performance on several different datasets. In next section we will present how XGBoost actions and apply to our dataset to solve prediction problem whether a person is infected to Melasma or not.

III. MACHINE LEARNING MODEL

1) XGBoost algorithm

XGBoost, designed with speed and performance, is a new machine-learning algorithm that has been widely applied successfully by the machine learning community in applications and competitions taking place on Kaggle. XGBoost stands for eXtreme

Gradient Boosting which deals with decision trees algorithms, applies techniques for merging decision trees, smooths training loss, and performs regularization. Following are four attributes that have made XGBOOST so successful [5], [8], [13]:

- Proportional reduction of leaf nodes (pruning) which improves model generality. It is important that the weak learners have skill but remain weak. There are a number of ways that the trees can be constrained. A good general heuristic is that the more constrained tree creation is, the more trees you will need in the model, and the reverse, where less constrained individual trees, the fewer trees that will be required.

- Newton Boosting which finds the minima directly instead of reducing the slope, making the learning process faster. The predictions of each tree are added together sequentially. The contribution of each tree to this sum can be weighted to slow down the learning by the algorithm. This weighting is called a shrinkage or a learning rate. Each update is simply scaled by the value of the “learning rate parameter ν ”. Similar to a learning rate in stochastic optimization, shrinkage reduces the influence of each individual tree and leaves space for future trees to improve the model.

- Additional random parameter which reduces the correlation between trees, ultimately improving group strength. A big insight into bagging ensembles and random forest was allowing trees to be greedily created from subsamples of the training dataset. This same benefit can be used to reduce the correlation between the trees in the sequence in gradient boosting models. This variation of boosting is called stochastic gradient boosting at each iteration a subsample of the training data is drawn at random from the full training dataset. The randomly selected subsample is then used, instead of the full sample, to fit the base learner.

- The only penalty of the tree. Classical decision trees like CART (Classification and regression tree) are not used as weak learners, instead a modified form called a regression tree is used that has numeric values in the leaf nodes (also called terminal nodes). The values in the leaves of the trees can be called weights in some literature.

Input: a training set $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, loss function $L(y, F(x))$ a differentiable function, number of weak learner M and learning speed α .

Output: Find an objective function $F^*(x) = F^*_{(M)}(x) = \sum_{m=0}^M F_m^*(x)$, that minimizes the expected error function.

1. Initialize the model with the constant value

$$F_\phi^*(x) = \arg \min_{\phi} \sum_{i=1}^N L(y_i, \phi).$$

2. For $m=1$ to M

a. Compute “gradient” $g_m(x_i)$ and “hessians”

$$h_m(x_i) = \left[\frac{\partial L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)} \right]_{F(x) = F_{(m-1)}^*(x)}$$

$$g_m(x_i) = \left[\frac{\partial^2 L(y_i, F(x_i))}{\partial F(x_i)^2} \right]_{F(x) = F_{(m-1)}^*(x)}$$

b. Recomputed the learning function using the training set $\left\{ x_i, -\frac{g_m(x_i)}{h_m(x_i)} \right\}_{i=1}^N$ by solving the following optimization problem:

$$\phi_m = \arg \min_{\phi \in \Phi} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{2} h_m(x_i) \left[-\frac{g_m(x_i)}{h_m(x_i)} - \phi(x_i) \right]^2,$$

$$F_m^*(x) = \alpha \phi_m(x).$$

c. Update the model: $F_{(m)}^*(x) = F_{(m-1)}^*(x) + F_m^*(x)$.

3. Returned result $F^*(x) = F^*_{(M)}(x) = \sum_{m=0}^M F_m^*(x)$.

A part of XGBoost's decision tree diagram with our melasma dataset in Figure 6.

Figure 6. A part of XGBoost's decision tree diagram

2) Model uses for predicting Melasma.

Input data to build and train the model of prediction Melasma is the dataset of a study on clinical characteristics and some factors related to Melasma in women in 2016 provided by Quyhoa National Leprosy Dermatology Hospital with of 795 data samples [11]. The goal is to find the outcome

variable ($y = \text{Results}$; non-infected = 0, infected = 1). The findings show that there are 238 Melasma infected cases and 557 non-infected cases. Gradient boosting is one of the most powerful techniques for building predictive models and we have used XGBoost to build our predictive model with 67% dataset used for training set and 33% for testing set.

A benefit of using gradient boosting is that after the boosted trees are constructed, it is relatively straightforward to retrieve importance scores for each feature.

Generally, importance provides a score that indicates how useful or valuable each feature was in the construction of the boosted decision trees within the model. The more an attribute is used to make key decisions with decision trees, the higher its relative importance.

This importance is calculated explicitly for each attribute in the dataset, allowing attributes to be ranked and compared to each other.

Importance is calculated for a single decision tree by the amount that each attribute split point improves the performance measure, weighted by the number of observations the node is responsible for. The performance measure may be the purity used to select the split points or another more specific error function.

The importance features are then averaged across all of the decision trees within our model and showed in the Figure 7.

Figure 7. Importance level of features affecting the outcome

Important (influential) variables on the outcome (infected or non-infected) are: Birth control pills (9.5%), Family history (9.3%), Family Economy (8.8%), Month of pregnancy (8.7%), Location (8.6%), Melasma during pregnancy (6.2%) Pathology (5.1%), Year of bird (4%), Sun exposure at afternoon (4%), Number of pregnancies (3.8%),

Sun exposure at noon (3.7%), Sun exposure at morning (3.7), Number of hours of sunlight exposure (3.7%), Age of using cosmetics (3.5%), Education (3.5%) and Occupation, Religion, Using cosmetics, Number of births, Marriage, ..., which have little effect on the outcome.

XGBoost supports early stopping after a fixed number of iterations. Running on our dataset trains the model 67% of the data and evaluates the model every training epoch 33% test.

```

...
[51] validation_0-logloss:0.553238
[52] validation_0-logloss:0.552787
[53] validation_0-logloss:0.553458
...
[67] validation_0-logloss:0.558049
Stopping. Best iteration:
[52] validation_0-logloss:0.552787
    
```

We can see that the model stopped training at epoch 67 and that the model with the best loss was observed at epoch 52.

To evaluate our predictive model using XGBoost for this Melasma dataset, we approach some ways to evaluate the machine learning model's performance as below:

Cross validation: With variable Kfold = 10 we have fitting 10 folds for each of 81 candidates, totalling 810 fits with the best parameters across ALL searched params: {'gamma': 0.6, 'learning_rate': 0.1, 'max_depth': 10, 'n_estimators': 100} we obtain Cross Validation results: [0.66666667, 0.66666667, 0.71698113, 0.71698113, 0.69811321, 0.75471698, 0.81132075, 0.75471698, 0.67924528, 0.75471698] so Cross Validation Mean Accuracy: 0.722013.

Learning Curves: We can retrieve the performance of the model on the evaluation dataset and plot it to get insight into how learning unfolded while training. We can then use these collected performance measures to create a line plot and gain further insight into how the model behaved on train and test datasets over training epochs.

Figure 8 shows the logarithmic loss of the XGBoost model for each epoch on our training and test datasets.

Figure 9 shows the classification error of the XGBoost model for each epoch on our training and test datasets.

Figure 8. XGBoost Learning Curve Log Loss

From the Figure, it looks like there is an opportunity to stop the learning early, perhaps somewhere around epoch 40 to epoch 60.

Figure 9. XGBoost Learning Curve Classification Error

We see a similar story for classification error, where error appears to go back up at around epoch 60.

Confusion Matrix: A confusion matrix is a correlation between the predictions of a model and the actual class labels of the data points. Our predictive model using XGBoost for 795 records of Melasma dataset has Confusion Matrix in Figure 10.

In this: Positive (P): Observation is positive (eg. is infected). Negative (N): Observation is not positive (eg. is not infected). True Positive (TP): Outcome where the model correctly predicts the positive class (519). True Negative (TN): Outcome where the model correctly predicts the negative

class (192). False Positive (FP): Also called a type 1 error, an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the positive class when it is actually negative (39). False Negative (FN): Also called a type 2 error, an outcome where the model incorrectly predicts the negative class when it is actually positive (46).

Figure 10. Confusion matrix

Accuracy is what its literal meaning says, a measure of how accurate your model is.

Accuracy = Correct Predictions / Total Predictions.

By using confusion matrix, Accuracy = (TP + TN)/(TP+TN+FP+FN). In our predictive model using XGBoost algorithm Accuracy = (519+192) / (519+192+38+46) = 89.4%.

Precision-Recall Curves

Precision

Precision is a ratio of the number of true positives divided by the sum of the true positives and false positives. It describes how good a model is at predicting the positive class. Precision is referred to as the positive predictive value.

Precision (non-infected) = 92%

Precision (infected) = 83%

Recall

Recall is calculated as the ratio of the number of true positives divided by the sum of the true positives and the false negatives

Recall (non-infected) = 93%

Recall (infected) = 81%

Figure 11. Precision-Recall curve

F-Measure

F1-score (non-infected) = 93%

F1-score (infected) = 82%

ROC-AUC Curves

A useful tool when predicting the probability of a binary outcome is the Receiver Operating Characteristic curve, or ROC curve.

It is a plot of the false positive rate (x-axis) versus the true positive rate (y-axis) for a number of different candidate threshold values between 0.0 and 1.0. Put another way, it plots the false alarm rate versus the hit rate.

The true positive rate is calculated as the number of true positives divided by the sum of the number of true positives and the number of false negatives. It describes how good the model is at predicting the positive class when the actual outcome is positive.

The ROC-AUC curve below presents the accuracy of the model. ROC for "non-infected" is 0.93 and for "Infected" is 0.93 in Figure 12.

Figure 12. ROC-AUC of model

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we present steps of a data analysis process in practice and build a machine learning model using the XGBOOST algorithm to predict the possibility of a user getting infected to Melasma. With this approach, the proposed method has exploited existing community data together with data collected through surveys to help the machine learning model have higher than 89.4% accurate prediction results, which assists in the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of the disease, thereby helping to reduce the cost of treatment.

The machine learning model that predicts the risk of Melasma is packaged and embedded into the web application at <https://ramma.bvquyhoa.vn> to help users know the possibility of being infected to Melasma, and provide users with habits that may cause Melasma, so that the users can prevent it. Dermatologists use the application to contact patients and evaluate support to upgrade the model through expertise and practical results. The application updates the data once collecting enough new data (the model is set to be retrained each time 100 new data are inputted) to enhance the accuracy of the model.

In order to get higher accuracy for the model, it is necessary to collect community data of many individuals and from many different regions, though it would require a lot of effort, time and expense.

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